

Studying the relationship between organizational justice and level of employees organizational obligation in state organization of Rafsanjan.

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Abstract

Human, always have had a goal of executing and enforcing justice in society. Therefore, we need organizational justice in order to reach social justice. Organizational justice is a key factor in all aspects of organizational behaviors such as, job promotion, job responsibilities and reward system. Organizational justice and its different domains are the main determinant factors of behaviors such as organizational obligation and etc. The main goal of this research is to study the relationship between organizational justice and level of employees organizational obligation in state organizations of Rafsanjan.

This study has been done based on correlation method. 361 persons have been chosen randomly, among 1915 employees of state organizations of Rafsanjan. Two kinds of standard and revised questionnaires have been used for data gathering. Statistical data analysis has been done based on Pearson and Spearman methods by use of Spss program.

Results show that, there is a significant relationship between organizational justice and level of employees organizational obligation in state organizations of Rafsanjan. Therefore, based on the results of this research, it is necessary for a manager to enforce organizational justice in order to increase level of employees obligation in an organization. Also, It is necessary to have a well-defined definition of justice which can offers some practical approaches for enforcement of distributed justice, procedural justice and communicated justice.

Keywords: organizational justice, organizational obligation, distributed justice, procedural justice, communicated justice.

Introduction

Justice has been the main goal and concern of man for a long time, which can change a human and even a society. Therefore, justice and its enforcement is one of the necessities of human life which is also a kind of innate and intrinsic dignities of human being. (Brokner et.al, 2004:390)

It is not surprising that researchers of different sciences pay special attention to social justice. Based on ancient books such as Hamoorabi and other divine books, it is easily understood that early writers were mostly interested in social justice. These holy books are kinds of guide books for human that show them how to communicate with each other and allocating resources justly. In almost every culture, we can see some tales and legends about justice and other moralities. Since Platoon and Aristotle, one of the main concerns of western philosophers was also the importance of social justice. In fact, it is really natural for human to be worry about justice. (Afjeh, 2001: 321)

Organizational justice is an expression which explains the significant role of justice in organization and allocation of job opportunities. Organizational justice main concern is to behave justly in an organization. (Naami et.al, 2006: 6)

For a long time, philosophers have been believed that organizational justice could be a part of social justice. In each organization, there are some competitive goals such as the process of employees selection. Job applicants trying to find a job in an organization and organizations can only offer jobs for some of these applicants so, other applicants would lose these opportunities. It means that, organization would choose the applicants based on some evaluations. For example, the organization can use both selection-decision method which means decide to select one applicant or not, and selection evaluation method which means whether the selection has been done based on psychological evaluations and job interviews or not. Organization should be justice in this stage because it has an important effect on employees attitude

towards organizational justice. Justice, especially organizational justice is a precious subject in many different organizational behaviors. It has been claimed that, justice is the main and central virtue of an organization. (Mehdad, 2002:323)

The other key factor of an organization is obligation, which is a kind of psychological connection between employees and organization. Organizations should have a well-defined definition of organizational obligation and trying to increase the level of this factor in their employees in a way that employees become more loyal to organization and its principles. Organization success and its improvement is mainly depends on the process of applying human resources. It is clear that bigger organizations have much more problems than the smaller ones. Managers try to monitor employees and their behaviors continuously in order to be more successful. Today, organizational obligation has become the most important subject of psychological studies of industries and organizations. (Esmaeeli; 2000:27)

Organizational justice shows that employees are so sensitive and would pay especial attention to the level of justice in their organization. When organizations follow the principles of organizational justice it means that they pay more attention to their employees. Therefore, employees would become more obliged to their organization and a kind of bilateral relationship would then forms between employees and organizations. (Shekar kan,et.al; 2006, 88-89). So, it is clear that organizational justice has an important effect on employees satisfaction, obligation and job resignation. (Raz Nahan,2003:148).

2.1 Thesis statement

Everybody can imagine an inappropriate condition, but it is really difficult to deal with a global society in which justice has no place. One would easily recognize any kinds of injustice manner because it can have a great effect on ones feelings and attitudes. We need something more in order to be able to imagine a world in which no one pay attention to the others achievements or a world in which there is no role for reward and punishment systems, because it is really difficult to have such imaginations. (Afjeh, 2001:321).

Based on the findings of social sciences researchers, all scientific books include a definition of justice. Justice means, the distribution of rewards and punishments based on and in a social system. It also means, who get what and how? Whether managers and supervisors act justly or not? Are they optimistic to whatever they have done?

Justice is the main concern of every aspect of human being and everybody should know and understand it, because people are so sensitive about the manner they are being behaved. (Afjeh, 200,320).

Some of researchers believe that, equal theory is in fact, the theory of justice distribution, because the main focus of this theory is to distribute incomes in a way that everybody have an equal chance for living better and therefore it would be a motivation for employees. According to equal theory, if people feel they are being behaved unjustly, they would be motivated, and severely try to create a justice system. Therefore, those managers that try to solve injustice issue, temporarily, would face many different and serious problems. (Rezaeeyan, 2005:41).

Justice in organizations also means principles of distribution system. Inappropriate methods of distribution, misbehaving with employees, and some behavioral decisions would have a great effect on employees attitude towards organizational justice. (Afjeh, 2001:318).

Organizational justice is a multi-dimension structure which includes distributed justice, procedural justice, and communicated justice. Doing researches about organizational justice have a history of three decades. (Moorman;1991:845). Greenberg (1990), in his article about past, present and future of organizational justice states that,

results of these kinds of researches can be the determinant factors and base of organizational behaviors. (Naami, et.al, 2004: 85)

Organizational obligation is a psychological manner that shows the level of employees tendency to continue their cooperation with organization. Organizational obligation has so many different meanings, such as:

Organizational obligation is mental attitude of employees towards organization. It is a continuous process according to which employees could show their interests in organization improvement and success. (Majidi,1998;32). There are different views about organizational obligation among which we define two of them in this paper; attitudinal view and behavioral view. Attitudinal view means that employees have an emotive and attitudinal view about organizational obligation. These employees feel more obliged to organization and its goals, and it is believed that emotive obligation is much more stable than any other kinds of obligations. (Abbasi, 2001:18-20). Behavioral view means employees have no emotional and inner obligation to organization and they only show their interests because of self-advantageous like job promotion and etc. (Khaki, 1996).

Organizational obligation is an important issue and all organizations are so serious about it. Morehead (2005: 81-82) believe that organizational obligation can bring many positive advantageous for organizations such as:

- Organizational obligation can cause employees to be more disciplined.
- Organizational obligation cause employees to work harder and stay longer in organization.

On the other hand, organizational obligation can bring higher job performance, less job resignation and less job absence as the result. (Moghimi, 2001: 393)

Organizational justice is a boundary in which, all procedures and principles placed justly and employees can easily understand that their manager behaved them justly. Organizational justice has a great effect on increasing employees obligation. Results show that, there is a significant relation between organizational justice and level of employees positive obligation. (Jeddi, et.al,2000:37).

It is important that, different people in different places, have different understandings of justice and it would bring different results, too. For example, evaluating justice in organizations significantly predicts factors such as, organizational obligation, employees loyalty and job satisfaction. (Ambrose, cropanzano, 2003:15)

Therefore, the main goal of this research is to study the relationship between organizational justice and level of employees obligation.

Theoretical framework

A theory has different functions in a research, but one of the most important functions of a scientific theory is that by use of these theories we can have a more comprehensive research. Without a theoretical framework, research has no definite direction. (Naderi nasab, 2007: 54). In fact, theoretical framework is the base of what we have done on a research, a logical, developed, defined and comprehensive network which connects different variables of the research to each other through interviews, observations and research history. (Khaki, 2005:30).

It should be mentioned that each of the theories about organizational justice and organizational obligation cannot offer a comprehensive definition of these factors. They are just defining some aspects of organizational justice and organizational obligation. Therefore, in this research we use those scientific theories, each of which can offer a definition for one aspect of organizational justice and organizational obligation.

Results show that, employees judgment of the level of organizational justice have a great effect on their attitudes towards variables such as organizational obligation and managers performances. (Lind, et.al, 1998:2). In fact, Level of organizational justice show the level of managers respect to their employees and creates a kind of certainty that fortifies employees obligation to organization.(Lambert, 2003:158).

Joye and veet (1992: 297) believe that distributing organizational justice is a key factor for managers to reach their organizational goals. Therefore when employees feel that organization behaves justly with them, they would become more loyal and obliged to organization and level of organizational obligation will increase as its result.

In fact, organizational justice is an important motivation for employees and injustice behaviors would have a bad effect on employees ethical norms. In these situations employees try to leave their job or even confront with organization. On the other hand, in a more justice organization employees feel more obliged and do their best in order to have better job performances. (Afjeh, 2001:316).

Justice is one of the main requirements of every kind of social partnerships. Even in smallest and weakest organizations employees job continuity is merely depends on the level of organizational justice. In fact, the more justly organizations performing, the more loyal employees they have. Whereas, continuity of injustice behaviors would has negative effects on employees behaviors and their social relations. Therefore, justice is the necessity of social, cultural and political systems of a society. (Poor ezat, 2003:9).

Results show that, researchers agree that organizational justice is an important issue in all systems so that have a great effect on employees behaviors. It is also important that employees understanding of the level of justice in organization bring some specific organizational behaviors and attitudes as the result. (Ambors, 2002: 806).

Having an overall understanding of organizational justice especially distributed and procedural ones would have positive reactions of employees such as organizational obligation and job satisfaction. (Seers, 1989; Green, 1976)

Therefore, group factors such as organizational obligation, organizational identity and self-esteem and some attitudes such as employees confidence to their coworkers and managers, employees understanding of legitimacy of organizational policies and hierarchy, are all the result of employees judgment of justice. (Rzaeiyan,2005:82)

As a whole, scientists of organizational behaviors believe that injustice behaviors in organizations can cause any dangerous reaction. (Afjeh,2001:330)

Prevalence of injustice behaviors in a society may reduce job morale of employees and also changes their attitude towards social system, while justice behaviors would increase level of obligation and employees voluntary efforts for social goals. As a whole, justice keep people coherently near each other and injustice may take them apart. (Folger,Kropanzano, 1998:198).

Based on the aforementioned issues, it is clear that whenever employees see injustice behaviors in organization they would react both emotionally (less obligation) and morally (want to quit their jobs). (Ambrose, 2002:806).

Therefore, based on the results of some studies (such as Lind, Rezaeiyan, Afjeh, Joy and Veet) the writer decided to do a comprehensive research about the relationship between organizational justice and level of employees obligation. Results show that employees feel more obliged to organization whenever they see justice behaviors.

Conceptual model of research

Predictor variable / criterion variable

Research hypothesis

Main hypothesis: There is a significant relationship between organizational justice and level of employees obligation in state organizations of Rafsanjan.

Subordinate hypothesis:

- There is a significant relationship between distributed justice and level of employees obligation in state organizations of Rafsanjan.
- There is a significant relationship between procedural justice and level of employees obligation in state organizations of Rafsanjan.
- There is a significant relationship between communicated justice and level of employees obligation in state organizations Rafsanjan.

Research methodology

This applied study has been done based on descriptive correlation method. Data gathering has been done by field studies. Statistical sample includes all employees of state organizations of Rafsanjan. Sampling has been done based on categorical randomly method. Sample volume is 361 based on Cookran formula.

Data gathering

Two kinds of closed questionnaires have been used for this research; Moorman, Mooler and Peers revised questionnaire have been used for evaluation of organizational justice, and Meeir & Alen questionnaire has been used for evaluation of organizational obligation.

Reliability and validity of the research

Research validity has been evaluated based on content validity method and the result shows 0.89 for organizational justice and 0.93 for organizational obligation. Research reliability has been evaluated based on retesting method and results of Spearman method show 0.88 for organizational justice and 0.84 for organizational obligation.

Data analysis

Descriptive statistic method has been used for variables description and for describing the relationship between variables Spearman and Pearson correlation methods have been used. All data analysis has been done by SPSS program and significant level of this study is 0.05.

Results

Main hypothesis: There is a significant relationship between organizational justice and level of employees obligation in state organizations of Rafsanjan.

H0: There is no significant relationship between organizational justice and employees obligation.

H1: There is a significant relationship between organizational justice and employees obligation.

Results of Pearson and Spearman correlation factors for organizational justice and organizational obligation are 0.423 and 0.453, respectively and significant level is 0.000 that is less than 0.05. Therefore, H1 accepted and there is a significant relationship between organizational justice and level of employees obligation in state organizations of Rafsanjan.

Table1. Results of Spearman and Pearson correlation factors on evaluation of the relationship between organizational justice and organizational obligation

Variable	Organizational obligation of employees							
Methods	Pearson			Spearman			Existence of the relation	Relation type
Organizational justice	Correlation factor	Significant level	number	Correlation factor	Significant level	number		
	0.423	0.000	361	0.453	0.000	361	yes	direct

First subordinate hypothesis: There is a significant relationship between distributed justice and employees obligation to organization in state organizations of Rafsanjan.

H0: There is no significant relationship between distributed justice and employees obligation.

H1: There is a significant relationship between distributed justice and employees obligation.

Results of Pearson and Spearman correlation factors for distributed justice and organizational obligation are 0.376 and 0.396, respectively and significant level is 0.000 that is less than 0.05. Therefore, H1 accepted and there is a significant relationship between distributed justice and level of employees obligation in state organizations of Rafsanjan.

Table2. Results of Spearman and Pearson correlation factors on evaluation of the relationship between distributed justice and organizational obligation

Variable	Organizational obligation of employees							
Methods	Pearson			Spearman			Existence of the relation	Relation type
distributed justice	Correlation factor	Significant level	number	Correlation factor	Significant level	number	yes	direct
	0.376	0.000	361	0.369	0.000	361		

Second subordinate hypothesis: There is a significant relationship between procedural justice and employees obligation to organization in state organizations of Rafsanjan.

H0: There is no significant relationship between procedural justice and employees obligation.

H1: There is a significant relationship between procedural justice and employees obligation.

Results of Pearson and Spearman correlation factors for procedural justice and organizational obligation are 0.418 and 0.432, respectively and significant level is 0.000 that is less than 0.05. Therefore, H1 accepted and there is a significant relationship between procedural justice and level of employees obligation in state organizations of Rafsanjan.

Table3. Results of Spearman and Pearson correlation factors on evaluation of the relationship between procedural justice and organizational obligation

Variable	Organizational obligation of employees							
Methods	Pearson			Spearman			Existence of the relation	Relation type
procedural justice	Correlation factor	Significant level	number	Correlation factor	Significant level	Number	yes	direct
	0.418	0.000	361	0.432	0.000	361		

Third subordinate hypothesis: There is a significant relationship between communicated justice and employees obligation to organization in state organizations of Rafsanjan.

H0: There is no significant relationship between communicated justice and employees obligation.

H1: There is a significant relationship between communicated justice and employees obligation.

Results of Pearson and Spearman correlation factors for communicated justice and organizational obligation are 0.288 and 0.311, respectively and significant level is 0.000 that is less than 0.05. Therefore, H1 accepted and there is a significant relationship between communicated justice and level of employees obligation in state organizations of Rafsanjan.

Table4. Results of Spearman and Pearson correlation factors on evaluation of the relationship between communicated justice and organizational obligation

Variable	Organizational obligation of employees							
Methods	Pearson			Spearman			Existence of the relation	Relation type
communicated justice	Correlation factor	Significant level	number	Correlation factor	Significant level	number	yes	direct
	0.288	0.000	361	0.311	0.000	361		

Conclusion

This research has one main hypothesis and three subordinate hypotheses, in which we study the relationship between organizational justice and level of employees obligation. Results of the main hypothesis show that there is a significant relationship between organizational justice and level of employees obligation. As Zahedi&Madani believe that, organizational obligation is a kind of dependent variable which has a close correlation with organizational justice. Results of this research are similar to the researches results of Chalbi&Habibi(1998), Borhani(2002), Dree&Aierson(1998), Dilbon&Martokchio(1998), Raylander(2003). The relationship between organizational obligation and organizational justice can be defined based on equal theory. If managers have equal behaviors with their employees, they would become more obliged to organization. (Madani,et.al, 2005:26)

Results of subordinate hypothesis also show that, there is a significant relationship between these variables. Results are as follow:

First subordinate hypothesis: statistical results show that there is a significant relationship between distributed justice and organizational obligation. Madani, et.al (2005:29) believe that a small decrease in level of distributed justice would decrease the level of employees obligation and loyalty.

Second subordinate hypothesis: statistical results show that there is a significant relationship between procedural justice and organizational obligation. Folger & Kropanzano (1998), believe that procedural justice means, equality in all methods, mechanism and procedures of an organization for reaching its goal. Equality of these methods, mechanism and procedures evaluated based on the follow rules;

1.It should not be a prejudicial method, mechanism or procedure, 2.it should considers the advantages of all employees,3.it should be corrigible, 4.it should have an ethical base, 5. It should focus on accurate alteration 6.it should create a kind of sustainable justice distribution. Folger & Kanovski(1989) believe that, procedural justice has some advantages that are: 1.organizational obligation, 2.employees would be more intent to continue their cooperation with organization, 3. Organizational allegiance, 4. Employees would trust more on managers, 5. Satisfaction of all decision-making, 6.more job efforts, 7.more job function. (Nazar pour; 2007:24)

Third subordinate hypothesis: statistical results show that there is a significant relationship between communicated justice and organizational obligation. In fact, communicated justice is a process in which manager transfer communicated justice to his employees. This kind of justice merely depends on different aspects of communication process (level of politeness, honesty and respect) that exist between sender and receiver of justice. Since, the main determinant factor of communicated justice is manager behaviors, therefore, this kind of justice have a close relationship with emotional and behavioral reactions of managers. Therefore, if managers do not observe the rules of communicated justice, their employees would have negative reactions to their managers instead of the organization, so the employee would be unsatisfied with his manager and have no obligation to the manager and not to the organization.(Hossein zadeh,et.al; 2007:22)

Suggestions

1. Statistical results show that there is a significant relationship between organizational justice and level of employees obligation, and based on these results, it has been suggested that managers pay more attention to the distribution of justice in organization especially for their reward system and division of labor, in order to increase the level of organizational obligation, organizational identity, self-respect and many other factors that rely on employees judgments of justice distribution.
2. Based on the results, it is clear that organizations would be able to observe organizational justice in order to have more obliged employees and have a competitive advantage.

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